

TOPIC: INTERPRETATION OF THE IMAGE OF WOMEN IN CONTEMPORARY STORIES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6885132>

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Abstract: *the article reveals the image of women in the stories of the current literary process and focuses on the importance of the image of a woman in fiction.*

Key words: *woman, Femininity, "Woman" story, will, Mahzuna.*

Addressing the image of women in Uzbek literature, creating their various images began to appear in our prose works created in the early years of the 20th century. We can cite Kumushbibi, Zaynab ("O'tkan kunlar"), Zebi ("Kecha va kunduz"), Unsin ("Dahshat"), Gulnor ("Qutlug qon"), Saida ("Sinchalak") and others. Although, in all these works, the image of women did not rise to the level of leading characters, they served to reveal the intended purpose of the work to one degree or another. In the modern Uzbek literature, such writers as Khurshid Dostmuhammad, Erkin Azam, Nazar Eshonqul, Isajon Sultan, Ulug'bek Hamdam, Kochkor Norqabil, Luqman Borikhon, Zulfia Kurolboy's daughter are active in our social life on an equal footing with men. or in some aspect of this life, the images of women with their own place occupy an important place.

The character of Mahzuna in Khurshid Dostmuhammad's story "Mahzuna" is described very carefully by the writer. Uzbek women's idiom and high education are embodied in her. When she agrees to go to the party without changing her husband's opinion, we can see that she is innocent and does not think of hurting someone's heart. During the party, another man's crush on her upsets her, and even after she comes home, she is disgusted with herself. In these places, his idiom was manifested. He feels like a complete stranger among the participants of the party. Seeing women who are raising a glass freely and saying askiya on an equal footing with men, praise burns in the fire of modesty. "Maksadjon's brother, who had become emaciated by sitting in such circles, urged him to the table by saying two or three times, "Take it and sit down to eat." "Makhzuna hums

under the ground to her husband as if to say, "speak more slowly," the author describes this situation.

Despite being a stranger to this circle, Makhzuna stood like a newly opened flower among the withering flowers, attracting everyone's attention with her youth, beauty, and shyness. This situation may have seemed normal for European-educated women participating in such circles where men and women had equal rights. Even, according to European ethics, this situation is considered as a victory of a woman, her superiority over others. Through the story "Mahzuna", the writer expressed in the lines of the work that beautiful qualities should be embodied in women.

"Makhzuna didn't understand, she was in trouble, she said that she would cry because of her humiliation," is how her situation is described. The worst thing is that the actions of Bori Sobitovich, an official who is clearly trying to find a pure honor, are shown sympathy by the young and old sitting in the circle, even by his wife. This period learned to exchange all moral norms and national honor for a single attractive thing called interest, and could not refrain from sacrificing even Mahzuna in the path of its abominable goal. At the end of the party, Bori Sobitovich kisses the hands of all the women like European gentlemen. The women were even proud of it, and squealed like nothing else, which horrified Mahzuna even more. In this story, Mahzuna is depicted as a sad flower among creatures.

In the story "Mahzuna" by Khurshid Dostmuhammad, the image of a woman is one of the images illuminated in a unique way. This work was created in the 90s of the last century. The work is distinguished from other works by its artistic and psychological interpretation, which compares the conflict between the Sharovian morality and the oriental woman. In the story, the image of internal conflicts of the national character comes out through the image of Mahzuna.

Zulfiya Kuroloy's story "Ayol" describes Nazokat's endurance, will and struggle for life, as if she embodies all the will in the world. In this story, there is a character of a woman who is always hoping for life. When creating this image, the writer instilled in her more power than men. Through the image of femininity, we can understand all the emotions embodied in women.

The writer Zulfia Kuroloy's daughter, through the story "Love and Hate", shows that she can be a person who can understand the human heart and be shoulder to shoulder even in the good and bad days of life. In this story, by depicting the image of Abdullah, who breaks the human heart and has a dry heart, he artistically describes that such people are hateful people who do not understand the human heart and human value. It is

commendable that the writer showed in this story that human life does not consist of darkness, but that there are also good people in the work through the character of Polat.

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